

HYGIENE OF PREGNANT WOMEN AND ITS SOLUTIONS, HYGIENE OF CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS, HYGIENE OF SEXUAL LIFE, HYGIENE OF VISION, HYGIENE OF MEN AND HYGIENE OF PREGNANT WOMEN.

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Abstract: The important factors of hygiene of children and adolescents, hygiene of sexual life, hygiene of vision, hygiene of men and hygiene of pregnant women, which are one of the current issues of today, were interpreted in the article. In this regard, the interpretations of great doctors are given. The objective and subjective factors of hygiene of children and adolescents, hygiene of sexual life, hygiene of vision, hygiene of men and hygiene of pregnant women are explained. In Uzbekistan, information is given on the activities related to the hygiene of children and adolescents, the hygiene of sexual life, the hygiene of vision, the hygiene of men and the hygiene of pregnant women.

Keywords: hygiene, diet, venereal disease, hypertensive disease

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Hygiene of children and adolescents is a branch of hygiene; deals with issues of maintaining and strengthening the health of children and adolescents from infancy to 17-18 years of age. It is the task of Child and Adolescent Hygiene to study how living conditions, education and work affect the development and health of the growing organism and, based on this, to develop hygiene measures that help the healthy growth and proper development of the young generation. His recommendations can be personal, that is, they can apply to each individual child and to a specific group of children. Hygiene of children and adolescents studies the influence of external environmental factors on the child's organism, its life activities, education, and develops measures necessary for the harmonious and harmonious development of the growing generation, both physically and spiritually.

Study and maintenance of health of children and adolescents. For this, it is necessary to study the influence of biological and social factors, external environment and general laws of development on the organism of children and adolescents. Determining the causes of diseases related to each age makes it possible to determine and implement measures for the prevention of the disease. Physical development of the current young generation is determined by using anthropometric methods along with regular health check-ups (medical examinations).

Children should be accustomed to the rules of personal hygiene from a very young age. Timely alternation of the main physiological processes in a child - sleep, wakefulness, feeding (sucking) is of great importance, especially in the first year of the child. Eating (sucking), sleeping, etc. at certain hours every day. has a good effect on the child's growth and development, especially on the nervous system. It is necessary to follow the procedure of breastfeeding the child at a certain time (every 3-3.5 hours). Creating comfortable conditions for the young child to always sleep at a certain time and wake up at a certain time, keep him calm when he sleeps, and when he is awake, influence the organs of sight and hearing in different ways (talking words of adults, drawing the child's attention to colorful, sonorous toys), changing the position of the body (hold the child from time to time or lay him on his stomach). The younger the child, the more his body needs rest and sleep. Let him walk in the open air (even in winter) for at least 2 hours every day,

must be played. Then the blood gets oxygenated and the exchange processes in the body go smoothly.

Hygienic activity of children and adolescents. In this regard, the main issue is to determine the performance of children based on their health and to gradually increase it, as well as to take measures to prevent fatigue. Based on this, an age-appropriate agenda is introduced for preschool, kindergarten, and school-aged children. Taking into account the characteristics of the growing organism, the training schedule of schoolchildren is determined differently depending on their age. The time allocated for preparing lessons at home is 1-1.5 hours for 1st grade students, 1.5-2 hours for 3rd-4th grade students, 2 hours for 5th-6th grade students, 2.5-3 hours for 7th-8th grade students, It should be 3-4 hours for 9-10 graders. 10-15 minutes after every 40-45 minutes while the child prepares for the lesson. he needs to rest. It is good for children to engage in various games, sports, and useful work after classes so that they do not get tired of preparing lessons.

Sexual hygiene is measures taken to prevent diseases of the genitals, as well as venereal diseases, to ensure the health of the child to be born, and the strength of the family.

Men's sexual hygiene includes keeping the genitals clean, abstaining from casual sex to prevent the transmission of venereal diseases, etc. k. consists of

It is necessary to wash the genitals with warm water every day, to keep the genitals clean when the boy is still a baby, and as he grows up, it is necessary to get used to washing the genitals with soap and wiping them dry. It is not suitable for young children to wear tight trousers and pants, otherwise, it can lead to genital warts or infection and inflammation (phimosis).

Women's sexual hygiene. Anatomical-physiological characteristics of the female body (menstruation, pregnancy, childbirth, breastfeeding), as well as special

cleanliness is required to protect and prevent genital diseases and venereal diseases.

From infancy, the external genitalia should be washed every morning and evening with marrow (boiling) water or a semi-pink solution of potassium permanganate. Before washing the genitals, wash hands with soap and water.

Since a girl does not have sex hormones in infancy and childhood, her genitals have special anatomical and physiological characteristics; the epithelium of the vagina consists of 2-3 layers of cells (40-50 layers in an adult woman), there are no special microorganisms in the vagina - vaginal rods. Because of this, various inflammatory diseases easily occur in this organ.

Measles, scarlet fever and other common diseases can cause infection in the vagina. There are even cases of worms exiting the rectum and entering the vagina. In this case, the skin and mucous membranes are scratched due to the girl's itchiness, infection enters and inflammatory diseases occur. This can lead to more serious consequences - hymen, vaginal obstruction or chronic inflammatory diseases - colpitis (inflammation of the vagina) and others.

Items used for genital hygiene should be kept separately in a clean place, and no one should touch them. It is necessary to always keep an eye on the state of the genitals of girls: observe cleanliness, regularly wash the genitals and the area between them, frequently change underwear, boil and iron them, girls' clothes, towels, etc.) separate storage and h. k.

Puberty of a girl child requires special attention. It is necessary to explain to her in advance the onset of menstruation, its essence and that it is not a disease, but a physiological state, so that she does not get confused if menstruation begins unexpectedly.

In addition to keeping the body clean and washing the external genitalia during menstruation, it is necessary to take additional hygiene measures. During this period, it is necessary to be careful of colds, flu and other (infections), not to bathe in open spaces, bath, and not to wear heavy work. Only a light shower is allowed.

A woman living with her husband should pay particular attention to sexual hygiene and attend a women's consultation at least once a year.

If you notice changes in the genitals (pain, heavy or low menstrual blood, fainting, etc.), it is necessary to consult a doctor. The hygiene measures mentioned above are also carried out during the climacteric and old age periods of a woman's life. In general, if both a woman and a man fully follow sexual hygiene, any unpleasantness can be avoided.

- Vision hygiene in ophthalmology practice is not limited to daily eye care and prevention of inflammatory processes, damage and foreign bodies

entering the eye. Human eye hygiene in the literal sense requires conscious regular prevention of the following eye diseases, as well as minimization of factors that reduce vision:

- Excessive eye strain and fatigue (excessive visual load);
- Unacceptable microclimate in rooms (excessive air conditioning, dusting), improper diet, harmful habits, unfavorable natural conditions (for example, staying in the sun for a long time);
- Use of contact lenses: violation of the rules of wearing and maintaining them;
- Infectious eye diseases (conjunctivitis, keratitis, etc.) due to non-observance of hygiene and prevention rules;
- Chronic eye diseases, including those related to aging ("dry eye" syndrome, glaucoma, cataracts, changes in the retina during aging);
- Misalignment of refraction (farsightedness, nearsightedness, astigmatism) or insufficient/excessive coordination with glasses and/or contact lenses; Injuries related to the profession, sports activities, foreign objects falling into the eyes (sand, dust, etc.);
- Eye diseases associated with general diseases (diabetes, hypertension, neurological diseases)
- In addition, elementary eye hygiene that parents teach their children from infancy is not neglected.
- Elementary rules of eye hygiene:
- Wash in clean running water in the morning and in the evening, clean the hardened youth in the corners of the eyes;
- Use only personal hygiene equipment (towels, pillowcases, handkerchiefs);
- Do not touch the face and eyes with unwashed hands;
- Do not use low-quality or expired cosmetics.
- The tear film consists of three layers - mucin, water and lipid layers. The composition of the outer lipid layer is called meibum (after the scientist Heinrich Meibom, who discovered this substance). The function of the lipid layer is to protect the tears from drying out by shining. Meibum is very important in the hygiene of the human eye, because it protects the surface of the eye from infections and dust.
- When a person sleeps, he does not think about the hygiene of the eye organs, his body temperature decreases. Part of the meibum thickens and collects as discharge on the inner surface of the eye and in the corners of the eye. By the way, an increase in ambient temperature also changes meibum - this condition can be observed in the bathroom.

- Pathogenic micro-organisms attack the accumulated tears, besides, the production of new tears is disrupted, therefore the first rule of eye hygiene is to wash the eyes with clean running water in the morning. If a person's meibomian glands fail and dry crust accumulates in the corners of the eyes, it is permissible for this person to meet an ophthalmologist and prescribe a drop medicine that normalizes the activity of the meibomian glands.

- Pregnant woman hygiene

- In addition to eating, a pregnant woman must strictly monitor personal hygiene. Every day he should spend enough time in the fresh air, move actively, but not overwork and under no circumstances lift weights. It is very useful for expectant mothers to do special exercises.

- During pregnancy, you should avoid noisy companies, many people, and you should not visit places where people smoke. In the summer, it's great to spend time in the sun, just not long, no more than 20 minutes a day. It contributes to the formation of vitamin D in the female body. Expectant mothers should sleep at least 8-9 hours a day. And be sure to avoid stress and negative emotions.

- Intimate hygiene for pregnant women includes a daily shower, morning and evening (as during pregnancy, the woman sweats more), as well as washing the external genitalia with warm water and soap. Douching should be avoided during pregnancy. Special means hygiene products for pregnant women are sold in pharmacies, they do not contain artificial ingredients that cause allergies or irritation and are completely safe for the health of the expectant mother.

- Clothes and shoes of a pregnant woman should be comfortable and made of natural materials. Special attention should be paid to choosing a bra. It should perfectly match the shape and size of the breast.

- Hygiene rules for pregnant women in breast care include the following procedures:

- grinding the nipple with a terry towel in a circular motion;

- Take air baths 10-15 minutes before going to bed;

- massage the mammary glands 2-3 times a day for 3-4 minutes.

- during pregnancy, observing personal hygiene, it is necessary to regularly wash the chest with water at room temperature.

- Pregnant sex life: sexual hygiene during pregnancy

- With a successful pregnancy, you should not refrain from sex, because the endorphins produced during orgasm have a good effect on your unborn child, and a similar orgasmic contraction of the uterus during childbirth will be produced in your child. give pleasure, not conditioned reflex and pain. The male sex hormones, nutrients and enzymes contained in the seed have a beneficial effect on your body.

- However, direct sex should be avoided in the last weeks before delivery.
- Enjoying sex during pregnancy is different for every woman. The problem of sexual activity during this period is often discussed by spouses. Sometimes people have a misconception about sex while carrying a child. Hormonal changes that occur in a woman's body in the first weeks of pregnancy, as a rule, reduce libido. For men, it remains the same. Against the background of diseases that appear in the first trimester of pregnancy, sexual activity decreases sharply. It can be assumed that this is a defensive reaction. In fact, frequent orgasms in the first months of pregnancy can cause spontaneous abortion. Some women lose interest in sex due to poor health. Sexual attraction increases in the second trimester. Well-being improves, libido increases. This is due to an increase in general blood flow in the body of a pregnant woman, an increase in secretion in the vagina, and an increase in the sensitivity of erogenous zones. Improved blood supply to the area
 - genitalia can enhance pleasure.
 - The breast becomes more sensitive to stroking. Many married couples find that sex life during pregnancy is different, including more caressing, tenderness and kissing.
 - When talking about sexual hygiene during pregnancy, it should be noted that the absence of fear of pregnancy allows you to enjoy sex more. A woman's ability to achieve orgasm increases significantly during sexual intercourse. Many women report that they experienced more than just sexual satisfaction during pregnancy for the first time. Men's understanding of sex also changes. Some of them worry that having sex can harm the child or cause premature birth. If you follow the hygiene of sexual activity during pregnancy, calm down, these fears have no reason, because the baby is reliably protected by the fetal bladder in the womb, and the birth can be born only if the time of their appearance is close. Others are confused by the presence of a witness in sex. Since sexuality can change during pregnancy, talk about mutual feelings. This will help you meet each other's needs and avoid misunderstandings.
 - The main requirement for the sexual hygiene of a pregnant woman with the normal birth of a child is to minimize intimate life in the first 2-3 and the last 1.5-2 months. If you have any questions, be sure to ask your doctor.
 - The main ways microbes and bacteria enter the body
 - The hygiene of a pregnant woman is very important, because the child must be protected from any virus, infectious disease and bacteria. The ways microbes enter the body are as follows:
 - oral cavity;

- dirty hands;
- dirty clothes;
- external genitalia.
- Basic rules of personal hygiene
- The hygiene of a pregnant woman is a very delicate and delicate matter, which includes many details. However, before going into detail, these basic rules should be remembered and followed:

- Take a cool or warm shower every day.
- Washing should be done several times a day if possible.
- It is better to refuse to visit baths and saunas.
- You cannot take a hot bath for a long time.
- It is better to limit swimming in water bodies, because in addition to harmful microorganisms, there is a strong excitement, which can have a negative effect on the fetus.

- Nails should be shortened so that dirt containing pathogenic microbes does not accumulate under them.

- Oral hygiene of pregnant women should be especially careful, because teeth are especially affected during pregnancy.

- All hygiene products (toothbrushes, towels, towels) must be individual.

- Summary

- Pregnancy is a pleasant and at the same time very responsible state. Expectant mothers should pay close attention to hygiene and nutrition so that the child grows up healthy and strong. During pregnancy, a woman's body becomes very vulnerable to germs and infections. Therefore, you need to strengthen it from the inside with high-quality nutrition and protect it from the outside.

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